

FACULTY OF MEDICINE, PUBLIC HEALTH, AND NURSING (FK-KMK)

GADJAH MADA UNIVERSITY (UGM)

Survey Instrument

Analysis of the Implementation of Health Service Benefits for People with Disabilities
in Achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC)

Respondent: Person with Disability
Instrument Code: 1A

Area Code:

- Buleleng Regency - 0362
- Denpasar City - 0361
- Bantul Regency - 0274
- Yogyakarta City - 075
- Kupang Regency - 0380
- Kupang City - 0381

Enumerator Code :

Opening

Good [morning/afternoon/evening].

My name is _____. I am an enumerator from the Center for Health Policy and Management, Faculty of Medicine, Public Health, and Nursing, Gadjah Mada University (PKMK FK-KMK UGM).

I would like to ask you some questions and have a discussion for about 60 minutes, if you agree.

Before we start, I will give you an information sheet and a consent form. The information sheet explains this activity in more detail.

Your participation is voluntary. You may choose not to answer any question that makes you uncomfortable. You may stop the interview at any time. All information you give will be kept confidential.

We will also give a small token of appreciation.

If you agree to be interviewed, please sign the consent form.

If you have any questions about this study or UGM, you may contact us using the phone number or email listed on the information sheet.

A. General Information of Respondents

This section asks about your identity, education, work, social assistance, and health insurance.

Respondent Identity

This section collects personal data for follow-up activities, such as interviews and other research methods.

Respondent Number:

[Area Code / Sample Code]

How is your health condition today?

(Overall physical and mental health)

1. Good
2. Not good

A1. Name: _____

A2. Gender:

1. Woman
2. Man

A3. Age: _____ years

A4. Phone number / Mobile / WhatsApp: _____

A5. Home address

(Street, alley, and house number): _____

A6. Village / Sub-district: _____

A7. City / Regency:

1. Buleleng Regency
2. Denpasar City
3. Bantul Regency
4. Yogyakarta City
5. Kupang Regency
6. Kupang City

A8. Province:

1. Bali
2. DI Yogyakarta
3. East Nusa Tenggara

A9. Marital status:

0. Not married
1. Married
2. Widowed (spouse has passed away)
3. Divorced

Education

A10. Are you currently attending formal education?
(Respondents aged 18–59 years)

0. No → Go to A12
1. Yes → Go to A11

A11. What level of education are you currently attending?

1. Junior high school / equivalent
2. Special junior high school
3. Senior high school/equivalent
4. Special senior high school
5. Package A / B / C
6. Diploma
7. Bachelor's degree (S1) or higher
→ After this, go to A15

A12. Have you ever attended formal education?

0. No → Go to A14
1. Yes → Go to A13

A13. What is the highest level of formal education you have completed?
(The highest level you finished or graduated from)

0. Did not complete elementary school
1. Graduated from elementary school / equivalent
2. Graduated from junior high school / equivalent
3. Graduated from special junior high school
4. Graduated from senior high school / equivalent
5. Graduated from special senior high school
6. Completed Package A / B / C
7. Graduated from higher education / university
→ After this, go to A15

A14. Why did you not attend formal education?

0. Disability made learning difficult
1. School was difficult to reach (transport / roads)
2. Financial problems
3. Doctor did not allow

4. Family did not allow
5. School buildings and facilities were not accessible
6. Lack of suitable teachers
7. No need
8. Other, please specify: _____
→ After this, go to A15

Informal Education

A15. Have you ever attended informal education?
(*Training, literacy classes, or learning outside school*)

0. No → Go to A18
1. Yes → Go to A16–A17

A16. How many times have you attended informal education?
_____ times

A17. When was the last time you attended informal education?
_____ month
→ After this, go to A19

A18. Why did you not attend informal education?

0. Disability made participation difficult
1. Difficult access (transport / roads)
2. Financial problems
3. Doctor did not allow
4. Family did not allow
5. Facilities were not accessible
6. Lack of instructors
7. No need
8. Other, please specify: _____
→ After this, go to A19

A19. Do you currently have a job?

0. No → Go to A21
1. Yes → Go to A20

A20. What kind of work do you do?
(*More than one answer allowed*)

1. Government employee
2. TNI / Police
3. Teacher / Lecturer
4. Private employee (staff)
5. Factory / office support worker (OB, security)

6. Trader (goods)
7. Food seller
8. Self-employed – goods production
9. Self-employed – service provider
10. Farmer (land owner)
11. Fisherman (boat owner)
12. Farm owner
13. Laborer (construction, driver, farm worker, fisherman)
14. Other, please specify: _____
→ After this, go to A22

A21. Why do you not have a job?
(More than one answer allowed)

1. Disability condition
2. Health condition that needs regular care
3. Retired
4. Still in training
5. Still in school
6. Supported by family
7. Difficult to find suitable work
8. Limited job information
9. Have not looked for work yet
10. Parents or partner do not allow
11. No specific reason
12. Other, please specify: _____
→ After this, go to A22

A22. In the last year, did you receive the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP)?

0. No → Go to A24
1. Yes → Go to A23

A23. How much PIP assistance did you receive in the last year?

Rp _____
7777777777 = Do not remember

A24. In the last year, did you receive the Family Hope Program (PKH)?

0. No → Go to A26
1. Yes → Go to A25

A25. How much PKH assistance did you receive in the last year?

Rp _____
7777777777 = Do not remember

A26. In the last year, did you receive Rastra/food assistance?

0. No → Go to A28
1. Yes → Go to A27

A27. How much rice assistance did you receive?

_____ kg
7777777777 = Do not remember

A28. Do you know about Social Rehabilitation Assistance (ATENSI)?

1. Yes → Go to A29
2. No → Go to A32

A29. Have you ever received ATENSI assistance?

1. Yes → Go to A30
2. No → Go to A32

A30. What type of ATENSI assistance did you receive?

1. Food and clothing
2. Temporary shelter
3. Health services → If option 3, go to A31
4. Education services
5. Identity document

A31. What type of health assistance did you receive from ATENSI?
(More than one answer allowed)

1. Health insurance registration
2. Help paying health costs
3. Transportation to health facilities
4. Accommodation during outpatient care
5. Referral assistance
6. Administrative assistance
7. Assistance during treatment
8. Other, please specify: _____

Health Insurance

Enumerator note: Explain types of health insurance using SHOWCARD.

A32. What health insurance do you have?
(More than one answer allowed)

1. BPJS Health / KIS / ASKES / Jamkesda → Go to A34
2. Private insurance → Go to Section B
3. Do not have insurance → Go to A33

A33. Why do you not have health insurance?

(More than one answer allowed)

1. Do not know how to register
 2. No access to registration
 3. Do not know about health insurance
 4. Cannot afford to pay
 5. Do not want health insurance
- After this, go to Section B

A34. Who keeps your BPJS/KIS/ASKES/Jamkesda card?

1. Self
2. Parent
3. Spouse
4. Child
5. Other family member
6. Companion
7. Village official
8. Health center staff
9. Other: _____

A35. Can you show your BPJS/KIS/ASKES/Jamkesda card?

0. No
1. Yes

A36. What type of BPJS Health membership do you have?

1. PBI (government-funded) → Go to Section B
2. PBPU (self-paid) 2 → Go to A37 and A38
3. PPU (paid by employer) → Go to A37
4. Non-worker (pension-based) → Go to A37

A37. What inpatient class does your health insurance cover?

1. Class I
2. Class II
3. Class III

A38. If PBPU, who pays your BPJS contribution each month?

1. Self
2. Parent
3. Spouse
4. Child
5. Non-family / others

B. Household Information

This section asks about family members and household expenses.

If the respondent is:

- the Head of Household, or
- the wife/mother, or
- an adult who knows the family and expenses,

→ ask the respondent directly.

If the respondent does not know or cannot remember:

- family members listed on the Family Card (KK), or
- monthly household expenses,

→ ask a family member living in the same house (mother, father, brother, or sister).

Enumerator Notes (Read Before Asking Questions)

Ask the respondent:

1. Do you know or remember the head of household and family members listed on the Family Card (KK) who live in this house?

1. Yes → ask the respondent directly
2. No → ask a family member who lives with the respondent

- If possible, ask to see the KK

2. Do you know your household expenses per month?

1. Yes → ask the respondent directly
2. No → ask a family member who lives with the respondent

Family Conditions

Enumerator note:

The Head of Household is the person written on the Family Card (KK).

A single house may have more than one KK, so there may be more than one head of household.

B1. How many family members are listed in the KK?

___ persons

B2. How many family members live in this house but are NOT listed in the KK?
___ persons

B3. How many heads of household (KK) are there in this house?
___ persons

B4. Does the Head of Household support family members living in this house?
(Head of Household on the same KK as the respondent)

1. Yes → go to B5–B7
2. No → go to B8

B5. How many family members does the Head of Household support for daily living expenses?
___ persons

B6. Whose living expenses are supported by the Head of Household?
(May choose more than one)

1. Husband
2. Wife
3. Child
4. Parent
5. Parent-in-law
6. Cousin
7. Grandchild
8. Nephew/niece
9. All family members
10. Other, specify: _____

- If “Child” is selected → answer B7
- If “Child” is NOT selected → go directly to B9

B7. How many children are listed in the KK?
___ children

→ After this, go to B9

B8. Why does the Head of Household NOT support family members?

1. No income
2. Income is not enough
3. Family members do not need support
4. Not willing to support
5. Other, specify: _____

→ After this, go to B9

Household Expenditure

This section asks about routine monthly expenses and non-routine yearly expenses.

Enumerator note:

If the respondent does not know or cannot remember the amount, write:

77.777.777.777

B9. How much does your household spend on food per month?

Rp _____

B10. How much does your household spend on non-food needs per month?

(Examples: electricity, water/PDAM, phone/internet, fuel)

Rp _____

B11. If you have BPJS Health (PBPU) and pay for one family:

How much do you pay per month for the family?

Rp _____

B12. If you have BPJS Health (PBPU) and pay only for yourself:

How much do you pay per month?

Rp _____

B13. If you have private health insurance:

How much do you pay for insurance premiums per month?

Rp _____

Other Non-Routine Expenses (Per Year)

Ask all questions.

If the respondent does not know or cannot remember the amount, write:

77.777.777.777

B14a. How much do you spend on religious or worship activities per year?

(Examples: religious ceremonies, zakat, offerings, Christmas, Chinese New Year)

Rp _____

B14b. How much did you spend on school fees in the last year?

Rp _____

B14c. How much did you spend on donations or social support in the last year?

(Donations to family, neighbors, friends, or others)

Rp _____

B15. Do you have someone who helps you with daily activities at home or outside the home?

1. No → go to B16
2. Yes → go to B17–B23

B16. Why do you NOT have a companion?

(Choose one)

1. I can do all activities by myself
2. I do not trust other people
3. I do not have money to pay
4. No one is available to help
5. Other, specify: _____

→ After B16, go to Section C

B17. Who is your MAIN companion?

(The person who helps you most of the time)

(Choose ONE)

1. Parent
2. Self
3. Spouse
4. Child
5. Grandchild
6. Other family member (cousin, nephew, in-law)
7. Friend
8. Neighbor
9. Professional nurse
10. Paid companion
11. Other, specify: _____

B18. What kind of payment do you give to your main companion?

1. Money
2. Goods / basic needs
3. No payment
4. Other, specify: _____

B19. How long has this companion helped you?

____ months

B20. What does your main companion help you with?

(May choose more than one)

1. Activities at home

2. Work or school activities
3. Outdoor activities
4. Going to health services
5. Other, specify: _____

B21. If your main companion cannot help, who helps you instead?
(May choose more than one)

1. Parent
2. Self
3. Spouse
4. Child
5. Grandchild
6. Other family member
7. Friend
8. Neighbor
9. Professional nurse
10. Paid companion
11. Other, specify: _____

B22. What does the temporary companion help you with?
(May choose more than one)

1. Activities at home
2. Work or school activities
3. Outdoor activities
4. Going to health services
5. Other, specify: _____

B23. What kind of payment do you give to temporary companions?
(May choose more than one)

1. Money
2. Goods / basic needs
3. No payment
4. Other, specify: _____

C. Disability Conditions

This section asks about type of disability, assistive devices, and therapy experience.

Enumerator Observation (Before Asking Questions)

The enumerator should first identify the respondent's disability by:

- existing respondent data, or
- assistive devices used, or
- visible physical condition

After observation, ask the respondent to explain their condition.

C1. What type of disability do you have?

(Based on Law No. 8 of 2016)

(May choose more than one)

1. Physical disability → go to C2
2. Visual disability → go to C3
3. Hearing or speech disability → go to C4

C2. Physical Disability

C2.1. What physical condition do you have?

(May choose more than one)

1. Amputation
2. Paralysis or stiffness
3. Paraplegia
4. Cerebral palsy
5. Effects of stroke
6. Effects of leprosy
7. Other physical condition
8. Other, specify: _____

C2.2. Do you use any assistive devices?

1. No → go to C2.3–C2.5
2. Yes → go to C2.6

C2.3. Why do you NOT use assistive devices?

1. No money
2. No information about assistive devices
3. Do not need assistive devices
4. Other, specify: _____

C2.4. How do you do activities at home WITHOUT assistive devices?

1. No difficulty
2. With difficulty

C2.5. How do you do activities OUTSIDE the home WITHOUT assistive devices?

1. No difficulty
2. With difficulty

→ After this, go to C5

C2.6. What assistive devices do you use?

(May choose more than one)

1. Crutches
2. Arm support/elbow stick
3. Wheelchair
4. Walker
5. Corset
6. Leg brace
7. Body brace
8. Prosthesis
9. Modified motorcycle/sidecar
10. Other, specify: _____

C2.7. Where did you get the assistive device?

(May choose more than one)

1. Community Health Center
2. Hospital
3. Therapy center
4. Medical supply store
5. Social organization
6. Government institution
7. Family or friends

C2.8. What is the ownership status of the assistive device?

1. Own device
2. Given as assistance
3. Rented
4. Donation / second-hand
5. Loan

C2.9. How did you obtain the assistive device?

(May choose more than one)

1. JKN–BPJS Health → go to C2.10–C2.21
2. Ministry of Social Affairs program → go to C2.22–C2.33
3. Local government social assistance → go to C2.34–C2.44
4. Bought with own money → go to C2.45–C2.55
5. Disability rehabilitation center/community → go to C2.56–C2.67

C2.10. Before you received the assistive device from BPJS Health, was there an assessment or examination?

(Assessment means checking your condition to choose the right device)

1. Examination of disability condition
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C2.11. Is the assistive device suitable for your disability needs?

(For example: different wheelchairs for different conditions)

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C2.12. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?

(Cooking, cleaning, washing, etc.)

1. Very helpful
2. Helpful
3. Not helpful

C2.13. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Very helpful
2. Helpful
3. Not helpful

C2.14. Does the assistive device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Very helpful
2. Helpful
3. Not helpful

C2.15. How long have you used the BPJS assistive device?

_____ months

C2.16. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C2.18
2. No → go to C2.17

C2.17. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

→ Continue to C2.18

C2.18. Have you ever changed your assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C2.19
2. No → go to C2.20

C2.19. How many times have you changed the assistive device?
____ times

→ Continue to C2.21

C2.20. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. Not yet time according to BPJS rules
4. Device not available in this area
5. Other, specify: _____

C2.21. What do you expect from BPJS Health regarding assistive devices?
(*May choose more than one*)

1. Higher price limit for assistive devices
2. Devices that better fit disability needs
3. More comfortable devices
4. More flexible replacement time
5. Easier application process

If the assistive device is from the Ministry of Social Affairs

C2.22. Was there an assessment before you received the assistive device?

1. Examination of disability condition
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C2.23. Is the assistive device suitable for your disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C2.24. Does the device help you with activities at home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.25. Does the device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.26. Does the device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.27. How long have you used this assistive device?

____ months

C2.28. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the device?

1. Yes → go to C2.30
2. No → go to C2.29

C2.29. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C2.30. Have you ever replaced the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C2.31
2. No → go to C2.32

C2.31. How many times have you replaced the device?

____ times

C2.32. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable

3. Replacement period not yet reached
4. Program only provides one device
5. Other, specify: _____

C2.33. What do you expect from the Ministry of Social Affairs program?
(May choose more than one)

1. Devices that better fit disability needs
 2. More comfortable devices
 3. Fair distribution of assistive devices
 4. Other, specify: _____
-

If the assistive device is from the Regional Government

C2.34. Was there an assessment before you received the assistive device?

1. Examination of disability condition
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C2.35. Is the assistive device suitable for your disability needs?

1. Yes
2. No

C2.36. Does the device help you with activities at home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.37. Does the device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.38. Does the device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.39. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the device?

1. Yes
2. No→ ask C2.40

C2.40. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C2.41. Have you ever replaced the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes→ ask C2.42
2. No→ ask C2.43

C2.42. How many times have you replaced the device?
_____ times

C2.43. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. Replacement period not yet reached
4. The program provides only one device
5. Other, specify: _____

C2.44. What do you expect from the Regional Government program?

1. Devices that better fit disability needs
2. More comfortable devices
3. Fair distribution of assistive devices
4. Other, specify: _____

If you bought the assistive device yourself

C2.45. How much did you spend on the assistive device?
Rp _____

C2.46. How did you decide which device to buy?
(May choose more than one)

1. Doctor's recommendation
2. Rehabilitation center recommendation
3. Family recommendation
4. Friend recommendation
5. Disability organization recommendation

6. Other, specify: _____

C2.47. Is the assistive device suitable for your disability needs?

1. Yes
2. No

C2.48. Does the device help you with activities at home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.49. Does the device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.50. Does the device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.51. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the device?

1. Yes
2. No → ask C2.52

C2.52. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C2.53. Have you ever replaced the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → ask C2.54
2. No → ask C2.55

C2.54. How many times have you replaced the device?
____ times

C2.55. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it

2. Still usable
 3. No money yet
 4. Waiting for assistance or donation
 5. Other, specify: _____
-

If the assistive device is from a Community / Rehabilitation Center

C2.56. Before you received the assistive device from the community/rehabilitation center, was there an assessment or examination?

(Assessment means checking your condition to choose the right assistive device)

1. Examination of disability condition
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C2.57. What is the name of the community or rehabilitation center that provided the assistive device?

C2.58. Is the assistive device suitable for your disability needs?

(Adaptive means the device fits your specific condition)

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C2.59. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?

(Cooking, washing, cleaning, etc.)

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.60. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.61. Does the assistive device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Helpful

2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C2.62. Have you ever repaired or adjusted this assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C2.64
2. No → go to C2.63

C2.63. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C2.64. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your disability condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C2.65
2. No → go to C2.66

C2.65. How many times have you replaced or changed the assistive device?
_____ times

C2.66. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. No further assistance from the community
4. Program provides only one-time assistance
5. Other, specify: _____

C2.67. What do you expect from the community/rehabilitation center program?
(*May choose more than one*)

1. More adaptive assistive devices
2. More comfortable assistive devices
3. Fair and equal distribution of assistive devices
4. Other, specify: _____

C3. Visual Disability

C3.1. What type of visual disability do you have?

1. Blind

2. Low vision

C3.2. Do you use any assistive devices for visual impairment?

1. Yes → go to C3.3
 2. No → go to C3.6
-

NoT using assistive devices

C3.3. Why do you not use assistive devices?

1. Cannot afford the cost
2. No information about assistive devices
3. Do not need assistive devices
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.4. Without assistive devices, how do you manage activities at home?

1. No difficulty
2. Have difficulty

C3.5. Without assistive devices, how do you manage activities outside the home?

1. No difficulty
 2. Have difficulty
-

If USING assistive devices

C3.6. What assistive devices for visual impairment do you use?

(May choose more than one)

1. White cane
2. Glasses
3. Braille tools
4. Magnifier
5. Open-book software
6. Digital magnifier
7. Screen reader
8. Scanner
9. Other, specify: _____

C3.7. Where did you obtain the assistive device?

(May choose more than one)

1. Community health center
2. Hospital
3. Therapy center
4. Medical equipment store
5. Social organization
6. Government institution
7. Family or acquaintances

C3.8. What is the ownership status of the assistive device?

1. Own device
2. Provided as assistance
3. Rented
4. Donation / second-hand
5. Borrowed

C3.9. What is the source of the assistive device?

(May choose more than one)

1. JKN–BPJS Health → C3.10–C3.21
 2. Ministry of Social Affairs (social assistance program) → C3.22–C3.33
 3. Regional government (local social assistance program) → C3.34–C3.44
 4. Bought with own money → C3.45–C3.55
 5. Community/rehabilitation center → C3.56–C3.67
-

If assistive device is from JKN–BPJS Health

C3.10. Before receiving the assistive device from BPJS Health, was there an assessment or examination?

1. Examination of disability condition
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.11. Is the assistive device suitable for your visual disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C3.12. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.13. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.14. Does the assistive device help you with exercise or mobility?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.15. How long have you been using the BPJS assistive device?
____ months

C3.16. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C3.18
2. No → go to C3.17

C3.17. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.18. Have you ever replaced the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C3.19
2. No → go to C3.20

C3.19. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
____ times

C3.20. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. Not yet time according to BPJS rules
4. Device not available in this area
5. Other, specify: _____

C3.21. What do you expect from the BPJS Health program regarding assistive devices?
(May choose more than one)

1. Higher price limit for assistive devices
2. More adaptive assistive devices

3. More comfortable assistive devices
4. More flexible replacement time
5. Easier application process

If assistive devices are from the Ministry of Social Affairs (Social Assistance Program)

C3.22. Before you received the assistive device from the Ministry of Social Affairs, was there an assessment?

(Assessment means checking your condition to choose the right device)

1. Disability condition examination
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.23. Is the assistive device suitable for your visual disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C3.24. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?

(Cooking, washing, cleaning, etc.)

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.25. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.26. Does the assistive device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.27. How long have you been using assistive devices from the Ministry of Social Affairs?

_____ months

C3.28. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C3.30
2. No → go to C3.29

C3.29. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.30. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C3.31
2. No → go to C3.32

C3.31. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
_____ times

C3.32. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. Replacement period has not yet passed
4. Program provides only one assistive device
5. Other, specify: _____

C3.33. What do you expect from the Ministry of Social Affairs program?
(May choose more than one)

1. More adaptive assistive devices
2. More comfortable assistive devices
3. Fair and equal distribution
4. Other, specify: _____

If assistive devices are from the Regional Government (Local Social Assistance Program)

C3.34. Before you received the assistive device from the regional government, was there an assessment?

1. Disability condition examination
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.35. Is the assistive device suitable for your visual disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C3.36. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.37. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.38. Does the assistive device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.39. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C3.41
2. No → go to C3.40

C3.40. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.41. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C3.42
2. No → go to C3.43

C3.42. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
_____ times

C3.43. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. The replacement period has not yet passed
4. The program provides only one assistive device
5. Other, specify: _____

C3.44. What do you expect from the regional government program?
(May choose more than one)

1. More adaptive assistive devices
2. More comfortable assistive devices
3. Fair and equal distribution
4. Other, specify: _____

If assistive devices were bought with your own money

C3.45. How much did you spend to buy the assistive device?
Rp _____

C3.46. How did you decide which assistive device to buy?
(May choose more than one)

1. Doctor's recommendation
2. Rehabilitation center recommendation
3. Family recommendation
4. Friend recommendation
5. Recommendation from disability organization
6. Other, specify: _____

C3.47. Is the assistive device suitable for your visual disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C3.48. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.49. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.50. Does the assistive device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.51. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C3.53
2. No → go to C3.52

C3.52. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.53. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C3.54
2. No → go to C3.55

C3.54. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
_____ times

C3.55. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. Do not have enough money
4. Still waiting for assistance or donation
5. Other, specify: _____

If assistive devices are from a Community / Rehabilitation Center

C3.56. Before you received the assistive device from the community or rehabilitation center, was there an assessment?

(Assessment means checking your condition to choose the right device)

1. Disability condition examination
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.57. What is the name of the community or rehabilitation center that provided the assistive device?

C3.58. Is the assistive device suitable for your visual disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C3.59. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?
(Cooking, washing, cleaning, etc.)

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.60. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.61. Does the assistive device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C3.62. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C3.64
2. No → go to C3.63

C3.63. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C3.64. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C3.65
2. No → go to C3.66

C3.65. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
_____ times

→ Continue to C3.67

C3.66. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it

2. Still usable
3. No further assistance from the community
4. Only one-time assistance provided
5. Other, specify: _____

C3.67. What do you expect from the community or rehabilitation center program?
(May choose more than one)

1. More adaptive assistive devices
 2. More comfortable assistive devices
 3. Fair and equal distribution
 4. Other, specify: _____
-

C4. Hearing and Speech Disability

C4.1. What type of hearing or speech disability do you have?

1. Deaf
2. Speech impairment
3. Deaf and speech impairment

C4.2. Do you use a hearing aid or communication assistive device?

1. Yes
 2. No
- No → go to C4.3 – C4.5
 - Yes → go to C4.6

C4.3. Why do you not use an assistive device?

1. Cannot afford it
2. No information about assistive devices
3. Do not need one
4. Other, specify: _____

C4.4. How do you manage activities at home without assistive devices?

1. No difficulty
2. With difficulty

C4.5. How do you manage activities outside the home without assistive devices?

1. No difficulty
2. With difficulty

If respondent uses an assistive device

C4.6. Where did you obtain the assistive device?
(May choose more than one)

1. Community Health Center
2. Hospital
3. Therapy center
4. Medical equipment store
5. Social organization
6. Government institution
7. Family or acquaintances

C4.7. What is the ownership status of the assistive device?

1. Own device
2. Rented
3. Donation or secondhand

C4.8. Where did you get the assistive device from?
(May choose more than one)

1. JKN–BPJS Health Program
2. Ministry of Social Affairs (social assistance)
3. Regional government (local social assistance)
4. Bought with own money
5. Community or rehabilitation center

If assistive device is from JKN–BPJS Health Program

C4.9. Before receiving the assistive device from BPJS Kesehatan, was there an assessment?

1. Disability condition examination
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C4.10. Is the assistive device suitable for your hearing or speech disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C4.11. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.12. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.13. Does the assistive device help you with exercise or movement?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.14. How long have you been using the assistive device from BPJS Kesehatan?
_____ months

C4.15. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C4.17
2. No → go to C4.16

C4.16. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C4.17. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C4.18
2. No → go to C4.19

C4.18. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
_____ times

C4.19. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. Replacement period not yet reached
4. Device not available locally
5. Other, specify: _____

C4.20. What do you expect from the JKN–BPJS Health Program?
(May choose more than one)

1. Higher maximum price coverage
 2. More adaptive assistive devices
 3. More comfortable assistive devices
 4. Flexible replacement period
 5. Simpler application process
-

If assistive device is from the Ministry of Social Affairs

C4.21. Before receiving the assistive device from the Ministry of Social Affairs, was there an assessment?

1. Disability condition examination
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C4.22. Is the assistive device suitable for your hearing or speech disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C4.23. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?
(Communicating with family, daily activities, etc.)

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.24. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.25. Does the assistive device help you with activities outside the home?
(Social interaction, community activities, mobility, etc.)

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.26. How long have you been using the assistive device from the Ministry of Social Affairs?
_____ months

C4.27. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C4.29
2. No → go to C4.28

C4.28. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C4.29. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C4.30
2. No → go to C4.31

C4.30. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
_____ times

C4.31. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. No replacement support available
4. Only one-time assistance provided
5. Other, specify: _____

C4.32. What do you expect from the Ministry of Social Affairs' assistive device program?
(*May choose more than one*)

1. More adaptive assistive devices
 2. More comfortable assistive devices
 3. Fair and equal distribution
 4. Regular replacement or follow-up support
 5. Easier application process
 6. Other, specify: _____
-

If assistive device is from the Regional Government social assistance program

C4.33. How did the Regional Government decide which assistive device you received?
(*How they checked what device you need*)

1. Disability condition was examined
2. Tried the device first

3. No assessment
4. Other, specify: _____

C4.34. Is the assistive device suitable for your disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C4.35. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?
(*Daily activities, communication, household tasks, etc.*)

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.36. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.37. Does the assistive device help you with activities outside the home?
(*Exercise, community activities, social interaction, etc.*)

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.38. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C4.40
2. No → go to C4.39

C4.39. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C4.40. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C4.41
2. No → go to C4.42

C4.41. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
_____ times

→ Continue to C4.43

C4.42. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. Replacement time has not been reached
4. Only one assistive device is provided
5. Other, specify: _____

C4.43. What do you expect from the Regional Government assistive device program?
(May choose more than one)

1. More adaptive assistive devices
 2. More comfortable assistive devices
 3. Fair and equal distribution
 4. Other, specify: _____
-

If you bought the assistive device yourself

C4.44. How much money did you spend on the assistive device?
Rp _____

C4.45. How did you decide which assistive device to buy?

1. Doctor's examination
2. Recommendation from rehabilitation center
3. Family recommendation
4. Friend recommendation
5. Recommendation from disability organization
6. Other, specify: _____

C4.46. Is the assistive device suitable for your disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C4.47. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.48. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful

2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.49. Does the assistive device help you with activities outside the home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.50. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C4.52
2. No → go to C4.51

C4.51. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C4.52. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C4.53
2. No → go to C4.54

C4.53. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
_____ times

C4.54. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. Do not have enough money
4. Waiting for help or donations
5. Other, specify: _____

If assistive device is from a community or rehabilitation center

C4.55. How did the community or rehabilitation center decide which assistive device you received?

1. Disability condition was examined
2. Tried the device first
3. No assessment

4. Other, specify: _____

C4.56. What is the name of the community or rehabilitation center?

C4.57. Is the assistive device suitable for your disability needs?

1. Yes, suitable
2. No, not suitable

C4.58. Does the assistive device help you with activities at home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.59. Does the assistive device help you with work or study?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.60. Does the assistive device help you with activities outside the home?

1. Helpful
2. Not helpful
3. Makes activities harder

C4.61. Have you ever repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Yes → go to C4.63
2. No → go to C4.62

C4.62. Why have you never repaired or adjusted the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Not needed yet
3. No repair service available
4. Other, specify: _____

C4.63. Have you ever replaced or changed the assistive device because your condition changed?

1. Yes → go to C4.64
2. No → go to C4.65

C4.64. How many times have you replaced the assistive device?
_____ times

C4.65. Why have you never replaced the assistive device?

1. Just received it
2. Still usable
3. No further assistance available
4. Only one assistive device provided
5. Other, specify: _____

C4.66. What do you expect from the community or rehabilitation center assistive device program?

(May choose more than one)

1. More adaptive assistive devices
2. More comfortable assistive devices
3. Fair and equal distribution
4. Other, specify: _____

Section C5. Experience of Therapy Services

C5. Have you ever received therapy for your disability or health condition?

1. No → go to C6
2. Yes → go to C7

C6. Why have you never received therapy?

1. Do not feel it is needed
2. Cannot afford the cost
3. Do not know where or what type of therapy is available
4. Other reason, specify: _____

C7. What type of therapy have you ever received?

(May choose more than one)

1. Physiotherapy
2. Occupational therapy
3. Behavioral therapy
4. Speech therapy
5. Surgery / operation
6. Therapy using medication
7. Traditional therapy, specify: _____
8. Other, specify: _____

- If Medication therapy (option 6) → go to C8
- Otherwise → go to C11

C8. What type of health insurance or support did you use to get medication therapy?

1. JKN–BPJS Health / KIS / ASKES
2. Private health insurance
3. Local government social assistance
4. Community donations
5. Paid by myself

- If Paid by myself → go to C9
- Otherwise → go to C11

C9. How much did you usually spend to buy the medication?

Rp _____

C10. Why did you pay for the medication yourself?

1. Health insurance does not cover the medication
2. Do not have health insurance
3. No assistance available for medication
4. Other reason, specify: _____

C11. Where did you usually receive therapy?

(Choose the main place)

1. Rehabilitation center → go to C13
2. Community health center (Puskesmas) → go to C18
3. Hospital → go to C22
4. Traditional therapy provider → go to C26

Rehabilitation Center

C13. How many times have you received therapy?

_____ times

C14. How long have you been receiving therapy?

_____ months

C15. What is the name of the rehabilitation center?

C16. What changes have you experienced after therapy?

(May choose more than one)

1. Better body movement

2. Better ability to do daily activities (eating, dressing, writing, etc.)
3. Better communication
4. No change
5. Other change, specify: _____

C17. Overall, how would you rate your condition after therapy?

1. Very good
 2. Good
 3. No change
 4. Bad
 5. Very bad
-

Community Health Center (Puskesmas)

C18. How many times have you received therapy?

_____ times

C19. How long have you been receiving therapy?

_____ months

C20. What changes have you experienced after therapy?

(May choose more than one)

1. Better body movement
2. Better ability to do daily activities
3. Better communication
4. Other change, specify: _____

C21. Overall, how would you rate your condition after therapy?

1. Very good
 2. Good
 3. No change
 4. Bad
 5. Very bad
-

Hospital

C22. How many times have you received therapy?

_____ times

C23. How long have you been receiving therapy?

_____ months

C24. What changes have you experienced after therapy?
(May choose more than one)

1. Better body movement
2. Better ability to do daily activities
3. Better communication
4. Other change, specify: _____

C25. Overall, how would you rate your condition after therapy?

1. Very good
 2. Good
 3. No change
 4. Bad
 5. Very bad
-

Traditional Therapy

C26. How many times have you received therapy?
_____ times

C27. How long have you been receiving therapy?
_____ months

C28. What changes have you experienced after therapy?
(May choose more than one)

1. Better body movement
2. Better ability to do daily activities
3. Better communication
4. Other change, specify: _____

C29. Overall, how would you rate your condition after therapy?

1. Very good
 2. Good
 3. No change
 4. Bad
 5. Very bad
-

Unmet Therapy Needs

C30. What therapy services do you need but have never received?
(May choose more than one)

1. Physiotherapy
 2. Occupational therapy
 3. Behavioral therapy
 4. Speech therapy
 5. Surgery / operation
 6. Medication therapy
 7. Other, specify: _____
-

D. Health Conditions and Use of Health Services

Current Health Conditions

D1. Do you have any of the following health conditions?
(Choose one main condition)

1. No chronic illness
2. High blood pressure
3. Diabetes
4. Joint, bone, or muscle pain
5. Heart disease
6. Chronic lung disease
7. Asthma
8. Recurrent migraines
9. Stroke
10. Depression
11. Anxiety
12. Gastric disease (ulcer, gastritis)
13. Cancer or tumor
14. Kidney failure
15. Tuberculosis (TB)
16. HIV
17. Other condition, specify: _____

- If 0 → go to D5
- If 1–77 → go to D2

D2. How did you know about this condition?

1. Doctor / hospital / health center / clinic
2. Midwife or nurse
3. Family member
4. Self-diagnosis
5. Other source, specify: _____

D3. In the last 12 months, have you taken medication for this condition?

1. No
2. Yes

D4. In the last 12 months, have you received special treatment for this condition?
(May choose more than one)

1. No
2. Surgery
3. Chemotherapy
4. Radiotherapy
5. Dialysis
6. Physiotherapy

Recent Illness

D5. In the last 12 months, have you been sick?

1. No
 2. Yes
- Yes → go to D6
 - No → go to D7

D6. What type of illness did you experience in the last 12 months?

1. Serious or long-term illness
(for example: dengue fever, asthma, heart disease, diabetes, stroke)
2. Mild illness
(for example: cold, cough, mild fever, headache, diarrhea)

→ Continue to D7

Health-Seeking Behavior

D7. What do you usually do when you are sick?
(Choose one main option)

1. Visit a health facility or health worker
 2. Buy medicine only
 3. Do nothing
 4. Use traditional medicine
- If 1 → go to D8
 - If 2 → go to D10
 - If 3 → go to D9
 - If 4 → go to D14

D8. Where did you go for treatment when you were sick?

1. Community Health Center (Puskesmas)
2. Hospital
3. Private doctor practice
4. Clinic
5. Nurse or paramedic
6. Midwife

→ Continue to D15

D9. Why did you not seek medical treatment when you were sick?
(May choose more than one)

1. Cannot afford the cost
2. No transportation available
3. Transportation cost is too expensive
4. Had bad experience with health services
5. Treatment does not help
6. No time (work or family duties)
7. Medicines or equipment are inadequate
8. Health workers lack skills
9. Do not know the location of the health center
10. Was refused treatment at the health center
11. Do not feel the need to go to a health center
12. Prefer traditional treatment
13. Other reason, specify: _____

→ Continue to D15

Buying Medicine Only

D10. Why do you only buy medicine without visiting a health facility?
(May choose more than one)

1. Do not have money to visit a doctor or facility
2. Health facilities are far from home
3. Illness is mild and only needs medicine
4. Faster and easier
5. Other reason, specify: _____

D11. Where do you usually buy medicine?

1. Pharmacy
2. Roadside stall
3. Mini market
4. Traditional herbal seller
5. Drug store

D12. Who usually buys the medicine?

1. Myself
2. Family member
3. Companion
4. Online application

D13. How do you know which medicine to take?

(May choose more than one)

1. Old prescription from a doctor
2. Advice from family/friends who are health workers
3. Advice from family or friends
4. Information from the internet
5. Television or radio advertisements
6. Other source, specify: _____

→ Continue to D15

Traditional Medicine

D14. Why do you choose traditional medicine instead of a health facility?

(May choose more than one)

1. Cheaper
2. Easy to access / close to home
3. Believe traditional medicine works better
4. Do not trust doctors or health facilities
5. No cost
6. Faster or more comfortable process
7. Other reason, specify: _____

→ Continue to D15

D15. Use of Community Health Center (Puskesmas) Services

D15.1. What services do you usually use at the Community Health Center?

D15.2. How often do you visit the Community Health Center?

1. 4 times in one month
2. 3 times in one month
3. 2 times in one month
4. Once a month

5. More than 4 times in one month

D15.3. How easy is access from your home to the Community Health Center?

1. Very difficult
2. Difficult
3. Easy
4. Very easy

D15.4. How long does it take to reach the Community Health Center from your home?
_____ minutes

D15.5. What transportation do you usually use to go to the Community Health Center?
(Choose one main option)

1. Bicycle
2. Motorcycle
3. Private car
4. Bus
5. Taxi
6. Gojek / Gocar
7. Boat
8. Walking
9. No transportation needed

- If 8 or 9 → skip D15.6 and D15.7

D15.6. How much do you usually pay for transportation (one visit)?
(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

Rp _____

D15.7. Do you need to pay for accommodation (hotel, boarding house, homestay) to access the Community Health Center?

(Yes and you do not remember the cost, write 888888888)

Rp _____

Transportation and Accommodation Assistance

D15.8. Do you receive any assistance for transportation or accommodation?

1. Yes → go to D15.9
2. No → go to D15.11

D15.9. Where does this assistance come from?
(May choose more than one)

1. Local government
2. Central government / ministry

3. International donors
4. Community or social organizations
5. Other source, specify: _____

D15.10. What type of assistance do you receive?
(May choose more than one)

1. Cash / money
2. Pick-up and drop-off transportation
3. Free accommodation / halfway house
4. Other form, specify: _____

Payment for Health Services at Community Health Centers

D15.11. How much did you pay for health services at the Community Health Center?
Rp _____

D15.12. How did you pay for these health services?
(May choose more than one)

1. JKN–BPJS Health / KIS / ASKES
2. Private health insurance
3. Social assistance
4. Paid by myself

(Enumerator: If more than one option is selected, ask about each payment source.)

D15.13a. How much was paid by BPJS Kesehatan for your health services?
(If you do not remember, write 8888888888)
Rp _____

- If only BPJS was used → go to D15.17
- If combined with other payments → continue to the relevant questions below

D15.13b. How much was covered by private health insurance?
(If you do not remember, write 8888888888)
Rp _____

- If only private insurance was used → go to D15.17
- If combined with other payments → continue below

D15.13c. How much was covered by social assistance?
(If you do not remember, write 8888888888)
Rp _____

- If only social assistance was used → go to D15.17
- If combined with other payments → continue below

D15.13d. How much did you pay with your own money?

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

Rp _____

→ Continue to D15.14

D15.14. Why did you need to pay with your own money?

(May choose more than one)

1. Some services were not covered by BPJS
2. Medicines were not covered
3. Private insurance did not cover all costs
4. Social assistance was insufficient
5. Chose to pay to get faster service
6. Other reason, specify: _____

D15.15. Did you have any additional health-related costs not yet mentioned?

1. No
2. Yes

- Yes, specify:
 - Type of cost: _____
 - Amount (Rp): _____

D15.16. How difficult was it for you to pay for health services at the Community Health Center?

1. Very difficult
2. Difficult
3. Not difficult
4. Not difficult at all

D15.17. Overall, how satisfied are you with the payment system for services at the Community Health Center?

1. Very satisfied
2. Satisfied
3. Neutral
4. Dissatisfied
5. Very dissatisfied

D15.13c. How much of the health care costs were covered by social security or assistance?

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

Rp _____

- If only assistance/social security was used → go directly to D15.17

- If combined with other payment methods → continue to D15.13b / D15.13a / D15.13d, then D15.15 – D15.17

D15.13d. How much did you pay for health services with your own money?

(If you do not remember, write 88888888)

Rp _____

- If only own money was used → go directly to D15.14
- If combined with other payment methods → go to D15.15 – D15.17

D15.14. What are the reasons you paid for health services using only your own money?

(May choose more than one)

1. Do not have health insurance / coverage
2. BPJS Health does not cover the treatment I need
3. The treatment I need is not covered by private insurance
4. BPJS Health does not cover the medicine I need
5. The medicine I need is not covered by private insurance
6. Faster health services
7. Better quality of health services
8. Other reasons, please specify: _____

→ After this, go to D15.17

If Services Are Paid Using Combined Payments

(For example: BPJS Health + private insurance, or BPJS Health + own money)

D15.15. What are the reasons the payment was combined with other payment methods?

(May choose more than one)

1. The medicine I need is not fully covered
2. The treatment I need is not fully covered by JKN/BPJS Health
3. I upgraded my inpatient class
4. The payment system was not clearly explained by the health facility
5. Other reasons, please specify: _____

D15.16. Reasons for Paying Despite Having BPJS Health

D15.16. If you have JKN/BPJS Health insurance, why did you still need to pay out of pocket?

(May choose more than one)

1. No problems
2. Long queue time
3. BPJS Health membership was inactive
4. The facility was not the required first-level health facility

5. Rejected by the health facility
 6. Limited hospitalization duration
 7. Concern about lower quality of health services
-

Perception of the Quality of Health Services at the Community Health Center

This section discusses your experience receiving health services at the Community Health Center, including obstacles, safety and comfort, inclusiveness, service time, and the referral process.

D15.17. What obstacles did you experience when accessing health services?
(May choose more than one)

1. Long queue time
2. BPJS Health membership could not be used
3. Private insurance could not be used
4. Did not get an inpatient room
5. Rejected by the health facility
6. Limited hospitalization time
7. No problems

D15.18. There are clear directional signs showing room layout, including the waiting area.
0. No

1. Yes, but not clear / difficult to understand
2. Yes, clear and easy to understand
3. Do not remember

D15.19. The waiting room has special seating or space for persons with disabilities.
0. Not accessible

1. Available but unclear
2. Available and clearly accessible
3. Do not remember

D15.20. Chairs in the waiting and examination rooms are accessible.
0. Not accessible

1. Some are accessible
2. All are accessible
3. Do not remember

D15.21. There is a wheelchair-accessible path or ramp.
0. Not available

1. Available but difficult to use

2. Available and easy to use
3. Do not remember

D15.22. There are guiding blocks for patients with visual impairment.

0. Not available

1. Available
2. Do not remember

D15.23. Loudspeakers are available and can be clearly heard.

0. Not available

1. Available
2. Do not remember

D15.24. Evacuation route instructions are available.

0. Not available

1. Available
2. Do not remember

D15.25. Health services respect you as a person with a disability.

0. No

1. Some staff are respectful
2. All staff are respectful
3. Do not remember

D15.26. Health staff can communicate well with you.

0. None

1. Some staff can communicate
2. All staff can communicate well
3. Do not remember

D15.27. Health staff can communicate using sign language.

0. None

1. Some staff can communicate
2. All staff can communicate well
3. Do not remember

D15.28. Availability of sign language interpreters.

0. Not available

1. Available but not helpful
2. Available and helpful
3. Do not remember

D15.29. Supporting media (visual aids, written materials, etc.) help the service process.

0. Not available

1. Available but not usable
2. Available and well used
3. Do not remember

D15.30. Staff show empathy toward patient anxiety or concerns.

0. Lack of empathy

1. Some staff show empathy
2. All staff show empathy
3. Do not remember

D15.31. Registration queue time

0. Fast

1. Normal
2. Slow
3. Do not remember

D15.32. Examination queue time

0. Fast

1. Normal
2. Slow
3. Do not remember

D15.33. Consultation/examination time

0. Satisfactory

1. Adequate
2. Not adequate
3. Do not remember

D15.34. Queue time for receiving medicines

0. Fast

1. Normal
2. Slow
3. Do not remember

D15.35. Who helped you obtain a referral from the Community Health Center?

(May choose more than one)

1. Health Center staff
2. Public Health Office
3. Family

4. Friends
5. Disability organizations / communities
6. No one

D15.36. What obstacles did you face when being referred from the Community Health Center to a hospital?

(May choose more than one)

1. Did not understand the referral process
2. Distance from home to referral hospital is far
3. Cost limitations
4. Other obstacles, please specify: _____

D16.1. What hospital services did you use?

(Write the service name, for example: outpatient care, inpatient care, emergency, maternity, surgery, etc.)

D16.2. How often did you use hospital services?

1. More than 4 times in one month
2. 4 times in one month
3. 3 times in one month
4. 2 times in one month
5. Once a month

D16.3. How easy is it to reach the hospital from your home?

1. Very difficult
2. Difficult
3. Easy

D16.4. How long does it take to travel from your home to the hospital?

_____ minutes

D16.5. What transportation do you usually use to go to the hospital?

1. Bicycle
2. Motorcycle
3. Private car
4. Bus
5. Taxi
6. Gojek / Gocar
7. Boat
8. Walking
9. Do not use transportation

D16.6. How much do you usually pay for transportation to the hospital (one trip)?
(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

Rp _____

D16.7. How much do you usually pay for accommodation (hotel, boarding house, homestay, etc.) when accessing hospital services?
(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

Rp _____

D16.8. Do you receive any assistance or program support for transportation or accommodation to access hospital services?

1. No → go to D16.11
2. Yes → go to D16.9 – D16.10

D16.9. Where does the transportation or accommodation assistance come from?
(May choose more than one)

1. Local government
2. Central government / ministry
3. Foreign donors
4. Community or social organizations
5. Other sources, please specify: _____

D16.10. What type of assistance did you receive?
(May choose more than one)

1. Cash or money support
2. Pick-up and drop-off transportation
3. Free accommodation / halfway house
4. Other types, please specify: _____

D16.11. How much did you pay for hospital services?
(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

Rp _____

D16.12. How were the hospital services paid for?
(May choose more than one)

1. JKN / BPJS Health / KIS / ASKES
2. Private insurance
3. Social assistance / social security
4. Paid with own money

D16.11. How much money did you spend for health services at the hospital?

Rp _____

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

D16.12. How did you pay for hospital services?

(You may choose more than one answer)

1. BPJS Health / JKN / KIS → answer D16.13a, then go to D16.17
 2. Private insurance → answer D16.13b, then go to D16.17
 3. Social assistance / social security → answer D16.13c, then go to D16.17
 4. Paid with own money → answer D16.13d and D16.14, then go to D16.17
- If more than one option → answer D16.13a–d as relevant, then D16.15–D16.17
(Do not answer D16.14)

D16.13. Amount Paid by Each Source

D16.13a. How much was paid by BPJS Health?

Rp _____

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

D16.13b. How much was paid by private insurance?

Rp _____

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

D16.13c. How much was paid by social assistance or social security?

Rp _____

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

D16.13d. How much did you pay with your own money?

Rp _____

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

D16.14. Why did you pay using your own money only?

(May choose more than one)

1. I do not have health insurance
2. BPJS does not cover the treatment I need
3. Private insurance does not cover the treatment I need
4. BPJS does not cover the medicine I need
5. Private insurance does not cover the medicine I need
6. Faster service
7. Better quality service

8. Other reason, please specify: _____

After this, go to D16.17

D16.15. Why did you use more than one payment method?
(May choose more than one)

1. BPJS does not fully cover the medicine
2. BPJS does not fully cover the treatment
3. I upgraded the inpatient class
4. The health facility did not explain clearly
5. Other reason, please specify: _____

D16.16. If you have BPJS, why did you still pay with your own money?
(May choose more than one)

1. No problem
2. Long waiting time
3. BPJS membership inactive
4. Not treated at the correct referral facility
5. Rejected by the health facility
6. Limited length of hospital stay
7. Fear of poorer service quality

D16.17. What problems did you experience when receiving hospital services?
(May choose more than one)

1. Long waiting time
2. BPJS cannot be used
3. Private insurance cannot be used
4. No inpatient room available
5. Rejected by the hospital
6. Limited length of stay
7. No problems

D16.18. Clear direction signs in the hospital

0. No
1. Yes, but not clear
2. Yes, clear and easy to understand
3. Do not remember

D16.19. Special waiting area for persons with disabilities

0. Not accessible
1. Available but unclear

2. Available and clear
3. Do not remember

D16.20. Chairs in waiting and examination rooms

0. Not accessible
1. Some are accessible
2. All are accessible
3. Do not remember

D16.21. Wheelchair access path

0. Not available
1. Available but difficult to use
2. Available and easy to use
3. Do not remember

D16.22. Guiding blocks for blind persons

0. Not available
1. Available
2. Do not remember

D16.23. Loudspeakers can be heard clearly

0. Not available
1. Available
2. Do not remember

D16.24. Evacuation route signs

0. Not available
1. Available
2. Do not remember

D16.25. Staff respect persons with disabilities

0. No
1. Some staff are respectful
2. All staff are respectful
3. Do not remember

D16.26. Staff can communicate well with you

0. None
1. Some staff
2. All staff

3. Do not remember

D16.27. Staff can communicate using sign language

0. None
1. Some staff
2. All staff
3. Do not remember

D16.28. Sign language interpreter availability

0. Not available
1. Available but not helpful
2. Available and helpful
3. Do not remember

D16.29. Supporting media (pictures, writing, tools)

0. Not available
1. Available but cannot be used
2. Available and useful
3. Do not remember

D16.30. Staff show empathy and understanding

0. No empathy
1. Some empathy
2. All staff show empathy
3. Do not remember

D16.31. Registration waiting time

0. Fast
1. Normal
2. Slow
3. Do not remember

D16.32. Examination waiting time

0. Fast
1. Normal
2. Slow
3. Do not remember

D16.33. Examination time with a health worker

0. Enough and satisfying

1. Just enough
2. Not enough
3. Do not remember

D16.34. Waiting time to get medicine

0. Fast
1. Normal
2. Slow
3. Do not remember

D16.35. Who helps you get a referral from the hospital to other health services?

(May choose more than one)

1. Hospital staff
2. Primary health care facility (e.g., Community Health Center)
3. Family
4. Friend
5. Disability organizations/disability communities
6. No one helps

D16.36. What problems do you face when getting a referral from the hospital to other services?

(May choose more than one)

1. Do not understand the referral process
2. Referral facility is far from my residence
3. Cost limitations
4. Other problems, please specify: _____

D17.1. What services do you use at the clinic / practicing doctor/midwife?

(May choose more than one)

1. Infant and child immunization
2. Child growth and development examination (weight–height monitoring)
3. Pregnancy check-up
4. Postpartum maternal check-up
5. Delivery/labor
6. Family planning/contraception (KB)
7. Nutrition consultation
8. Blood pressure check
9. Blood sugar check
10. Infectious disease examination (COVID-19, HIV, TB, malaria, diarrhea, dengue fever)
11. Treatment due to an accident
12. Minor illness treatment (fever, cough, cold, headache, etc.)
13. Follow-up outpatient care after hospital treatment
14. Inpatient care

15. Other services, please specify: _____

D17.2. How often do you use clinic / doctor / midwife services?

1. 4 times in 1 month
2. 3 times in 1 month
3. 2 times in 1 month
4. Once a month
5. More than 4 times in 1 month

D17.3. How is access from your residence to the clinic / doctor / midwife?

1. Very difficult
2. Difficult
3. Easy
4. Very easy

D17.4. How long does it take to reach the clinic/doctor / midwife from your residence?

_____ minutes

D17.5. What transportation do you use to go to the clinic / doctor / midwife?

1. Bicycle
2. Motorcycle
3. Private car
4. Bus
5. Taxi
6. Gojek / Gocar
7. Boat
8. Other water transport
9. Walk
10. Do not use transportation

D17.6. How much do you usually pay for transportation to the clinic/doctor/midwife?

Rp _____

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

D17.7. How much do you pay for accommodation (hotel, boarding house, homestay, etc.) when accessing clinic/doctor/midwife services?

Rp _____

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

D17.8. Do you receive any assistance or programs to cover transportation or accommodation costs?

1. No assistance → go to D17.9–D17.10
2. Yes, there is assistance → go to D17.11

D17.9. Where does the assistance come from?
(May choose more than one)

1. Local government
2. Central government / ministry
3. Foreign donors
4. Community or civil society organizations
5. Other sources, please specify: _____

D17.10. What type of assistance do you receive?
(May choose more than one)

1. Cash/money
2. Pick-up and drop-off transportation service
3. Free accommodation / halfway house
4. Other forms, please specify: _____

D17.12 How much money do you spend on health services at the clinic / doctor / midwife?

Rp _____

D17.13. How did you pay for these health services?
(May choose more than one)

1. BPJS Health / JKN / KIS → answer D17.14a, then go to D17.18
 2. Private insurance → answer D17.14b, then go to D17.18
 3. Social assistance / social security → answer D17.14c, then go to D17.18
 4. Paid with own money → answer D17.14d and D17.15, then go to D17.18
- If more than one option → answer D17.14a–d as relevant, then D17.16–D17.18
(Do not answer D17.15)

D17.14. Amount Paid by Each Source

D17.14a. How much was paid by BPJS Health?

Rp _____

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

D17.14b. How much was paid by private insurance?

Rp _____

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

D17.14c. How much of the health service cost is paid by social security?

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

Rp _____

- If only social security → go to D17.18
- If combined with other payments → answer D17.14a / D17.14b / D17.14d as relevant, then go to D17.16 – D17.18

D17.14d. How much do you pay with your own money?

(If you do not remember, write 888888888)

Rp _____

- If only own money → go to D17.17
- If combined with other payments → go to D17.15 – D17.17

D17.15 Why did you pay for health services only with your own money?

1. I do not have health insurance
2. BPJS Health does not cover the treatment I need
3. Private insurance does not cover the treatment I need
4. BPJS Health does not cover the medicine I need
5. Private insurance does not cover the medicine I need
6. The service is faster
7. The service is better
8. Other reason, please specify: _____

→ After this, go to D17.18 – D17.37

If Payment Is Combined

(For example: BPJS Health + private insurance)

D17.16 Why is the payment combined with other payment sources?

1. The medicine is not fully covered
2. BPJS Health does not fully cover the treatment
3. I upgraded the inpatient class
4. The health facility did not explain clearly
5. Other reason, please specify: _____

D17.17 If you have JKN/BPJS Health, why do you still pay out of pocket?

1. No problem
2. Long waiting time
3. BPJS membership is inactive

4. Not the correct first-level health facility
5. Rejected by the health facility
6. Limited hospitalization time
7. Health service quality is worse

D17.18 What problems do you experience when getting health services?

(Can choose more than one)

1. Long waiting time
2. BPJS Health cannot be used
3. Private insurance cannot be used
4. No inpatient room available
5. Rejected by the health facility
6. Limited hospitalization time
7. No problems

D17.19 Clear direction signs (including waiting room)

1. No
2. Yes, but not clear
3. Yes, clear and easy to understand
4. Do not remember

D17.20 Special waiting area for persons with disabilities

1. Not accessible
2. Available but unclear
3. Available and accessible
4. Do not remember

D17.21 Chairs in waiting and examination rooms

1. Not accessible
2. Some chairs are accessible
3. All chairs are accessible
4. Do not remember

D17.22 Wheelchair path

1. Not available
2. Available but difficult to use
3. Available and easy to use
4. Do not remember

D17.23 Guiding block for blind persons

1. Not available
2. Available
3. Do not remember

D17.24 Loudspeaker announcements

1. Not available
2. Available
3. Do not remember

D17.25 Evacuation route signs

1. Not available
2. Available
3. Do not remember

D17.26 Health staff respect you as a person with a disability

1. No
2. Some staff respect me
3. All staff respect me
4. Do not remember

D17.27 Staff can communicate with you clearly

1. No staff
2. Some staff
3. All staff
4. Do not remember

D17.28 Staff can communicate using sign language

1. No staff
2. Some staff
3. All staff
4. Do not remember

D17.29 Availability of sign language interpreters

1. Not available
2. Available but not helpful
3. Available and helpful
4. Do not remember

D17.30 Supporting media (pictures, boards, etc.)

1. Not available

2. Available but not usable
3. Available and helpful
4. Do not remember

D17.31 Staff show empathy to patient worries

1. No empathy
2. Some empathy
3. All staff show empathy
4. Do not remember

D17.32 Registration waiting time

1. Fast
2. Normal
3. Slow
4. Do not remember

D17.33 Examination waiting time

1. Fast
2. Normal
3. Slow
4. Do not remember

D17.34 Examination time

1. Satisfying
2. Enough
3. Not enough
4. Do not remember

D17.35 Waiting time for medicine

1. Fast
2. Normal
3. Slow
4. Do not remember

Referral Process

D17.36 Who helps you get a referral from the clinic to other services?

(Can choose more than one)

1. No one
2. Health center staff
3. Public health office

4. Family
5. Friend
6. Disability organization / community

D17.37 What problems do you face when referred from the clinic to the hospital?

1. Do not understand the referral process
2. The hospital is far from home
3. Cost problems
4. Other problem, please specify: _____

E. JKN / BPJS Health / KIS Membership

This section discusses respondents' experiences in obtaining and using JKN / BPJS Health / KIS.

It covers the registration process, payment of contributions for PBPJ, and use of the JKN Mobile Application.

E1 How did you obtain JKN / KIS / BPJS Health coverage?

1. Registered by the local government
2. Assisted by community organizations
3. Registered by myself

- If 1 → go to E3
- If 2 → go to E4
- If 3 → go to E5 and E6

E2 How did you find out that you were registered as a JKN / KIS / BPJS Health participant by the government?

1. From RT/RW
2. From village / sub-district / district government
3. When I was sick and receiving treatment at a health facility
4. From parents or family
5. From the community

E3 Why did you not register yourself as a JKN / KIS / BPJS Health participant?

1. Limited information
2. No access to registration

E4 Why did you register as a JKN / KIS / BPJS Health participant?

1. To get assistance or protection when sick
2. To get financial protection from illness
3. To meet administrative requirements

(Examples: job application, ID card requirements, house purchase, etc.)

E5 Where did you get information about JKN registration?

(Can choose more than one)

1. Local government (RT, village head, sub-district, district)
2. Social Affairs Office
3. Health Office
4. Civil society organizations
5. Health facilities
6. Social media
7. Television
8. Radio
9. Newspaper
10. Family

E6 If you are a PBPU participant, how do you pay your monthly contributions?

(Can choose more than one)

1. Pay directly at BPJS Health office
2. JKN Mobile application
3. Mobile banking
4. Bank ATM
5. Digital wallet (Gopay, OVO)
6. E-commerce (Shopee, Tokopedia)
7. Post office
8. Minimarket (Indomaret, Alfamart)
9. Other method, please specify: _____

E7 If you are a PBPU participant, have you ever been late in paying contributions?

1. No
2. Yes

E8 Yes, do you know how to resolve unpaid or late contributions?

1. No
2. Yes

E9 Yes, how do you resolve unpaid or late contributions?

1. Visit BPJS Health branch office
2. Use the JKN Mobile application

E10 Do you know how to change your first-level health facility (Faskes Tingkat I) in JKN?

(The first-level health facility is the primary health facility listed on the BPJS Health card.)

1. No
2. Yes

E11 Do you know the benefits provided by JKN / BPJS Health?

1. No
2. Yes

E12 What JKN / BPJS Health benefits do you know?

Use of the JKN Mobile Application

E13 Do you have the JKN Mobile application?

1. No → go to Section F
2. Yes → go to E14 – E17

E14 Have you ever used the JKN Mobile application?

1. No
2. Yes

E15 Why do you use the JKN Mobile application?

(Can choose more than one)

1. Check participant data
2. Pay contributions
3. Health self-screening
4. Change first-level health facility
5. Check hospital bed availability
6. Check contribution arrears
7. Doctor consultation
8. Other reason, please specify: _____

E16 What problems do you face when using the JKN Mobile application?

E17 What do you expect from the JKN Mobile application so it can better accommodate your disability needs?

F. Health Communication, Information, and Education

This section discusses respondents' experiences in seeking and obtaining information related to health and disability conditions.

F1 Have you ever looked for health information?

1. Never
 2. Once
- If 1 → continue to F2 – F10
 - If 0 → skip to F11 – F13

F2 What health information do you often look for?

F3 Where do you obtain the health information you are looking for?

1. Television broadcast
2. Radio broadcast
3. Video or image content on social media
4. Articles in online media
5. Articles in newspapers
6. Printed infographics in health facilities
7. Printed infographics in public places
8. Videos in health facilities
9. Videos in public places
10. Messages shared via WhatsApp, Line, or Telegram
11. Messages sent via SMS
12. Other sources, please specify: _____

F4 Who provides the health information?

1. Family
2. Friends
3. Neighbors
4. RT/RW head
5. Village head
6. Community leaders in the residential area
7. Religious leaders
8. Health workers
9. City, district, or provincial government
10. Central government
11. Disability organizations or communities
12. Artists or celebrities
13. Others, please specify: _____

F5 What obstacles do you face when seeking health information?

(Can choose more than one)

1. No captions or subtitles provided
2. No audio provided
3. Language used is difficult to understand
4. Other obstacles, please specify: _____

F6 Have you ever looked for information about your disability condition?

1. Yes
 2. Never
- If 1 → continue to F7 – F10
 - If 2 → skip to F11 – F13

F7 What information about disability conditions do you often look for?

1. Use of assistive devices
2. Characteristics of disability
3. Changes in disability conditions
4. Therapy services for disabilities
5. Other information, please specify: _____

F8 Where do you obtain information about disability conditions?

1. Television broadcast
2. Radio broadcast
3. Video or image content on social media
4. Articles in online media
5. Articles in newspapers
6. Printed infographics in health facilities
7. Printed infographics in public places
8. Videos in health facilities
9. Videos in public places
10. Messages shared via WhatsApp, Line, or Telegram
11. Social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, etc.)
12. Google or other web searches
13. Messages sent via SMS
14. Other sources, please specify: _____

F9 Who provides information about disability conditions?

1. Family
2. Friends
3. Neighbors
4. RT/RW head
5. Village head

6. Community leaders in the residential area
7. Religious leaders
8. Health workers
9. City, district, or provincial government
10. Central government
11. Disability organizations or communities
12. Artists or celebrities
13. Others, please specify: _____

F10 What obstacles do you face when seeking information about disability conditions?

1. No captions or subtitles provided
2. No audio provided
3. Language used is difficult to understand
4. Other obstacles, please specify: _____

F11 Who do you expect to provide information that is easy to understand and trustworthy?

1. Family
2. Friends
3. Neighbors
4. RT/RW head
5. Village head
6. Community leaders in the residential area
7. Religious leaders
8. Health workers
9. City, district, or provincial government
10. Central government
11. Disability organizations or communities
12. Artists or celebrities
13. Others, please specify: _____

F12 What media do you think can help you obtain health information that is easy to understand?

1. Television broadcast
2. Radio broadcast
3. Video or image content on social media
4. Articles in online media
5. Articles in newspapers
6. Printed infographics in health facilities
7. Printed infographics in public places
8. Videos in health facilities
9. Videos in public places
10. Messages shared via WhatsApp, Line, or Telegram
11. Social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, etc.)
12. Google or other web searches

13. Messages sent via SMS

14. Other media, please specify: _____

F13 What helps you understand information provided through media or communication tools?

1. Availability of sign language or written subtitles
2. Availability of braille
3. Availability of audio
4. Direct explanation from family members
5. Direct explanation from community leaders in the residential area
6. Direct explanation from health workers